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Abstract: The notion of sin begins within a theological framework. It is religion that gives sin its particular contours and that enables persons to recognize sin as a breach of rules, a rupture of relationship, a denial of what is wholesome and/or good, and, finally, the means to overcome it. Religions possess their particular and specific understandings or definitions of sin. A single clear common denominator seems absent whereby the meaningfulness of sin can be grasped. Perhaps the most that can be said about a shared understanding of sin is that an agent brings about the destruction of order originating from the divine and expressed in religion. Connected with this understanding are the following: conscience, the freedom exercised by the agent, accountability, the harmful effects of destroying order, guilt, repentance, forgiveness, restitution, punishment and mercy. Doing good is seen as acting virtuously whereas doing evil is sinning. Both these actions presuppose a religious tradition to which one belongs and in virtue of which a person experiences fulfilment or loss of oneself.

Keywords: Sin; Sin in Karl Rahner, Function of sin in Theology

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The Understanding of Sin and Its Function in the Theology of Karl Rahner

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The notion of sin begins within a theological framework. It is religion that gives sin its particular contours and that enables persons to recognize sin as a breach of rules, a rupture of relationship, a denial of what is wholesome and/or good, and, finally, the means to overcome it. Religions possess their particular and specific understandings or definitions of sin. A single clear common denominator seems absent whereby the meaningfulness of sin can be grasped. Perhaps the most that can be said about a shared understanding of sin is that an agent brings about the destruction of order originating from the divine and expressed in religion. Connected with this understanding are the following: conscience, the freedom exercised by the agent, accountability, the harmful effects of destroying order, guilt, repentance, forgiveness, restitution, punishment and mercy. Doing good is seen as acting virtuously whereas doing evil is sinning. Both these actions presuppose a religious tradition to which one belongs and in virtue of which a person experiences fulfilment or loss of oneself.

The Judaeo-Christian tradition puts great emphasis on the free choice of a person that is exercised in conformity with the will of God or against it. While there is mention of sins committed inadvertently, sin normally means a deliberate rejection of the covenantal relationship between God and persons. This rejection is seen taking place in the concrete circumstances of everyday life. Even so, a renewed offer of covenantal relationship on God's part along with a conversion of the person can rebuild the relationship between the person and God. The primary aspect of this relationship is God's graciousness to the person who owes his/her origin and preservation to God. Hence, even the Genesis account of creation is understood as establishing a covenant

between God and the persons created by God. The sin of Adam and Eve is essentially a rejection of God's covenantal relationship with the creature. The Genesis narrative tells of the catastrophic effects of that rejection, yet it highlights the promise to be realized in the future that will refound the covenantal relationship that had been broken by the sin of Adam and Eve.

However, the covenantal God described in the scriptural narrative is not one object among many others present in the cosmos at large. God is characterized by transcendence, mystery and a sense of the unconditional. Any naming of God—as in the case of concrete objects—is fraught with danger since it willy-nilly boxes God into a space that can be occupied only by a finite and created reality. God as the named reality in the Christian scriptures is distanced from God's creation—qualitatively and quantitatively—in an infinite way! When the breaking of relationships between human persons takes place, one can identify the dynamics that are present in that fracturing, but how does one understand the dynamics that are present between God and human persons? How does one elaborate a theological method that deals with sin in the world without reducing God merely to another object in creation? Can one draw out a metaphysics of sin when the finite and the infinite are to be considered in their specific identities/natures?

As a Christian theologian, Karl Rahner interprets sin in terms of his system of transcendentalism. He begins by sketching out his understanding of the human person vis-à-vis God, the transcendent reality. Freedom is that which characterizes a person, and it is only then that he begins treating of the reality of sin. Hence, this article first deals with the freedom of the human person in the world (his/her situatedness) created by God. After that, an attempt is made to explicate Rahner's understanding of sin in terms of that situation. Finally, the third and concluding section will offer some critical remarks on Rahner's understanding of sin and its function in his theology.

Part One: The Human Person in the World

In Rahner's understanding, one does not begin to understand the situation of the human person as sinful by subjecting him/her to an enquiry that does not take into account divine revelation. On the one hand, human persons are not self-sufficient creatures; they are separated

by a mysterious chasm from God, yet are dependent on that God for their being and final fulfilment. At the same time, persons are capable of true and radical freedom so that they can accept or reject God's offer of communion and eternal bliss. In both cases human responsibility is exercised. How and where does one begin to analyze the person in terms of freedom and/or self-determination?

The Human Person

A person is situated in the world not primarily in opposition to another but as one who is thrown into the world to be in a network of relationships that make up the world. The person is *Dasein*.¹ Heidegger, whose classes Rahner attended and found stimulating, holds that the very modes and vantage points that we employ to examine being are constitutive of that being's essential characteristics. The influence of the German poet Friedrich Hölderlin (1770-1843) and Holderlin's understanding of "inhabit" is reflected in Heidegger's and Rahner's approach to being. To be in the world is to live harmoniously in it and to the full.

Looking at something, understanding and conceiving it, choosing, access to it—all these ways of behaving are constitutive for our inquiry, and therefore are modes of Being for those particular entities which we, the inquirers, are ourselves... The entity which each of us is himself and which includes inquiring as one of the possibilities of its Being, we shall denote by the term "*Dasein*".²

The intelligibility of being does not come about as a result of our reasoning processes but is already present in its "there-ness". Keeping to the Heideggerian perspective of being a person, Rahner too takes into account the different attributes, or rather possibilities of being a person.

The human person is unable to construct a theology by merely viewing the situation in which he/she exists. It is not only reasoning—even when done within a faith perspective—that ensures a valid theology. In Rahner's own words:

In the primary and original sense theology is not a system of valid propositions constituted by human thought, but the totality of divine speech [God's total revelation] addressed by God himself to man, albeit

in human language. This word of God's revelation, thus already heard and grasped in an original unity of *auditus* and *intellectus*, can and should in turn be made by man the object of his enquiring, systematizing thought.³

Hence, one does not try to construct with the help of logic and/or natural philosophical knowledge alone a picture of evil since such an effort is no more than speculative. At most, it argues a disposition of true openness on the part of the human person.⁴

But the communication of God has taken place and continues to be an existential reality in the world of men and women. This communication has taken place through happenings in the history of men and women. These happenings are seen as "categorical" in that they are perceived against the horizon of transcendence that lies within the human spirit. The categorical may be understood as episodic happenings strung together and forming the history both of the world and of the human phenomenon. Human persons grasp the transcendence of God that is seen in the categorical events of history. The believer easily understands that the mysterious and transcendent God is present and mediated through the various elements and factors that make up creation (and therefore historical reality) but above all and most definitively in the person of Jesus Christ.⁵

This communication can be understood as God sharing the God-self with persons. This constitutes the supernatural existential.

God's self-sharing is in Rahner's phrase a "supernatural existential." The word "existential" (borrowed from Heidegger) indicates an aspect of human life, a reality of existence. A supernatural existential is a form not phenomenologically seen but held by faith to be real and present, "present in every person at least in the mode of an offer."⁶

A problem that is often associated with the supernatural existential is that the status of the natural is so magnified that it is treated as divine. Such an understanding would be counter to what is affirmed in *Dei Filius* of Vatican I regarding what we can know through our human intellect (natural reason), what is revelation proper—i.e. known by divine faith—and how it can be grasped by a God-given illumination. Human redemption takes place through grace but grace is without question a gift of God to humankind. Let us hear Rahner explain this point:

Without prejudice to the fact that it speaks of a free and unmerited grace, of a miracle of God's free love for spiritual creatures, the statement that man as subject is the event of God's self-communication is a statement which refers to absolutely all men, and which expresses an existential of every person. Such an existential does not become merited and in this sense "natural" by the fact that it is present in *all* men as an existential of their concrete existence, and is present prior to their freedom, their self-understanding and their experience. The gratuity of a reality has nothing to do with the question whether it is present in many or only in a few people.⁷

Already in *Hearers of the Word*, Rahner anticipates the charge that he has so identified the natural status of the person so that he/she seems graced by nature and not by the free gift of God.⁸⁸ (Translated by Michael Richards), Herder and Herder, New York, 1969, p 73, footnote 3.

Human Freedom

Rahner is aware of two basic types of freedom that the person is capable of exercising. Traditionally, one type is the 'freedom of choice' when an individual is supposedly neutral and decides for one thing rather than another.⁹ Another type is when 'self-realization' takes place so that an individual is able to realize himself/herself to a greater extent (as in some way envisaged in the *esse melius* of scholastic philosophy). Hence, 'self-realization rather than 'freedom of choice' is the characteristic of human freedom. This is so because the spirit of the human person transcends the concrete reality of a person.

It would be a complete misconception of the nature of freedom to try to understand it as the mere capacity of choice between objects given *a posteriori*, among which, besides many others, there is also God; so that God would only play a special role in the choice made by this freedom of choice from among these many objects on account of his own objective characteristics but not on account of the nature of freedom itself. Freedom only exists—as was seen explicitly by St. Thomas—because there is spirit understood as transcendence. (p 179)

It is decisive for the Christian understanding of freedom, however, that this freedom is not only made possible by God and is not only related to him as the supporting horizon of freedom of choice in

categories, but that it is freedom *vis-à-vis* God himself. This is the frightening mystery of freedom in its Christian understanding. Where God is understood in categories as merely one reality among others, as one of the many objects of freedom of choice—understood as a neutral capacity which is arbitrarily occupied with this and that—the statement that freedom of choice is choice even with regard to God would present no particular difficulty.¹⁰

The Radicalism of Human Freedom (Fundamental Option)

The intention of Rahner in identifying human freedom with a person's transcendence and, therefore, spirit is to highlight the overpowering and devastating consequences that follow from the exercise of human freedom. A person has the awesome power of accepting or rejecting the transcendent reality of God as presented to him/her in Christian revelation, and, more specifically, in Jesus Christ. In exercising this freedom the person becomes that reality which God intended he/she should be: finite transcendence fulfilling its finality!

Freedom never happens as a merely objective exercise, as a mere choice 'between' individual objects, but is the *self*-exercise of the man who chooses objectively; only within this freedom in which man is capable of achieving himself is man also free with regard to the material of his self-achievement. He can do or omit this or that in view of his own self-realisation that is inescapably imposed on him. This self-realisation is a task he cannot avoid and, in spite of all the differences within the concrete material of his self-achievement, it is always either a self-realisation in the direction of God or a radical self-refusal towards God.¹¹

Rahner's approach to human freedom, the understanding of its exercise and the possibility of saying "yes" or "no" to God provides the wherewithal for understanding the doctrine of the fundamental option.

The concrete freedom of man by which he decides about himself as a whole by effecting his own finality before God, is the unity in difference of the formal '*option fondamentale*' and the free individual acts of man no longer attainable by reflection, a unity which is the concrete being of the subject of freedom having-achieved-itself. In all

this, to emphasise this once more and explicitly, freedom—precisely speaking—is not the possibility of infinite revision, but the capacity to do something uniquely final, something which is finally valid because it is done in freedom. Freedom is the capacity for the eternal. (*emphasis mine*)¹²

Enough has been said about the human person in his/her situatedness in the world to understand how Rahner envisages the exercise of human freedom in a Christian economy of grace. His notion of the fundamental option is the outcome of his anthropology.¹³ Rahner's doctrine about the fundamental option seeks to demonstrate how the exercise of human freedom cannot be the compelling motive and reason for human self-fulfilment. In the ultimate analysis human fulfilment remains gift totally given by God in God's free self-communication.

The total decision by which man decides definitively about the whole of his reality, i.e. posits this totality itself in its freely determined finality (and an individual act can be called really and completely free only in so far as this happens), is a total decision that according to revelation belongs to the judgment of God alone. Man does indeed come ever closer to his finality in freedom as a *conscious* subject, but he cannot once more objectify this result of his freedom for himself, i.e. judge for himself and even less others in their total quality before God. The *Catholic* doctrine of faith declares that man cannot, while still a pilgrim on earth, have an absolutely certain judgment about his state of justification or eternal salvation. Even the *Protestant* doctrine of justification is not ultimately at variance with this point (in spite of all controversies) since, even for the Lutheran doctrine of justification, absolute fiducial faith always remains subject to temptation. This means also, therefore, that man cannot adequately reflect objectively and with absolute certainty on his free decisions. It means that freedom is really subjectivity and that subjectivity is in itself and in its self-presence a more original reality than individually existing objects which can be clearly determined by a previously conceived co-ordinate system of universal ideas.¹⁴

The doctrine of the fundamental option, as understood by Rahner, does not pretend to explain away the mystery of human sinfulness or the mystery of God's redeeming action that brings about the conversion of the person. It seeks to give substance to the human act of freedom in

the sight of God, places the human person totally in the arena of God's forgiving love and mercy, and attempts to present human choices in a more comprehensive perspective. It is in this context that the doctrine of the fundamental option is brought into play.¹⁵ Richard A. McCormick (Ref. Richard P. McBrien (general editor):

The HarperCollins Encyclopedia of Catholicism

HarperCollins Publishers, New York, 1995, p 594) says the following:

Whether it explains human choice satisfactorily, God's respect for that choice and the act of conversion to God's grace in a better way than theories that preceded it is a moot point. What Rahner does affirm is that the God revealed through Jesus Christ is eternally the God of love, of mercy and forgiveness, no matter what human intransigence may attempt and succeed in doing.

Part Two: Sin in the World

Freedom and Responsibility

The fact of sin is linked to responsibility. The human subject posits acts that help realize his/her selfhood in the world. Catholic theology interprets these actions as virtuous or sinful in so far as they are seen to accept or reject God's self-communication. Such an interpretation affects all men and women in the world because all persons are included in one divine plan of salvation.

The understanding of these concepts [freedom and responsibility] in the history of man's self interpretation has no doubt a long and variable history to which also belongs precisely the history of revelation and of Christian theology. Christian theology nevertheless presupposes a permanent nature in man which is preserved throughout the whole history of mankind even though it only becomes gradually conscious of itself in that history. It therefore presupposes also a permanent common knowledge about responsibility, even though this too has its own history. Otherwise, all men could not really be the subject and object of one divine salvation on the part of one and the same God in Jesus Christ within one unified history of salvation.¹⁶

Human freedom and responsibility are not experienced in an ambience where the human person is separated from that space where

God is present making available the offer of divine self-communication to the creature, but are exercised in that very space. A person

understands freedom as an autonomous self-possession of man before or even against God, but not in the sense that God's grace and mastery and the responsible exercise of freedom are realities encroaching on each other...The divine freedom and mastery are experienced from the outset as the reason for the possibility of the creature's responsibility and freedom, so that both grow in equal and not in inverse proportion...This is obviously what is meant by the Christian statement about man and his salvation and damnation...¹⁷

Freedom and Guilt

However, not every act of freedom is able to bring about the self-fulfilment and a total giving of oneself to God. This would be the oblique side of the exercise of freedom. Further, it is also part of human experience that a person does not know with absolute certitude that one is justified before God. At the same time, Catholic doctrine holds that there exist "material, objective and universally valid norms for the right or wrong exercise of this subjective freedom in the categorized material of the nature of man and of his world."¹⁸ Hence, the true and absolute condition of the person in his/her accepting or rejecting God's self-communication is not a matter that is unilaterally known by a person but is best left to the merciful judgment of a loving God! About guilt, Rahner has the following to say:

If...the relationship between guilt in the theological and in the ordinary sense is to be defined exactly, it must not be overlooked that it is not given to man to pass any ultimate judgment about guilt before God, in the form of a reflected objective statement either in his own case or in that of others. Hence it is impossible, even from the objective material, the spatio-temporal tangibility and the objective quality of human action, to get any clear idea for such definitive judgment about such a really existing guilt before God.

The true status of the human person must be faced. It is only God who is totally aware of the self, whereas the human person must contend with limited awareness and corresponding responsibility in knowing and understanding the self. If a person cannot be absolutely certain about

his/her state of grace, neither must we assume that—in every circumstance—a person who is acting wrongly is totally aware of what he/she is doing. In keeping with the presupposition of God making it possible for a person to posit a free act, it is God's judgment alone that validates the act of virtue or sin.

What then of the punishment due to sin that Christian teaching implies? There is no need of punishment being imposed from God's part as a form of "retribution":

there will no longer theologically speaking be any insurmountable obstacles to the thesis maintaining that all divine punishment is a connatural consequence of guilt flowing from the proper nature of guilt and need not be specially added by God: and that therefore God is the punisher of sin by having created the objective structures of man and of the world.

However, it is appropriate for the keeping of good order in society for civil authority to punish someone for the preservation of the common good. But this pattern must not be extended to God's way of dealing with persons.

Freedom and Sacramental Forgiveness¹⁹

The Christian offends against God but as a member of the Church. In committing sin, he/she "offends against *her* Spirit, against her mission and against the unquestioning obedience he owes to her." Even more, the Christian "renders the Church herself sinful in a certain regard." (p 137) Hence there is need to confess to the Church.

Binding and loosing refers to the ban imposed on the penitent who is kept away from the Lord's Supper till the ban is lifted. This is to make the person more intent on feeling his/her exclusion from the Eucharist and thus helping towards the process of conversion. (148)

The questions that had been raised regarding the "matter" in the sacrament of Penance arose from the fact that conversion—by doing penance, i.e. moral acts that enhanced the graced stature of the penitent—was a process present in the penitent. Yet the Church had to officially pronounce—effect rather than merely "declare"—its absolution so that

the penitent could take his/her place back in the eucharistic assembly. (162)

If the Church helps the penitent to overcome the guilt of sin and to experience grace in his/her heart, it is because the Church has already prayed and continues praying for him/her. The prayers recited before the absolution proper signify the Church's prayer. (pp 162-163)

The final point of arrival of the penitent is awareness that God has forgiven him/her through the ministry of the Church, thus fulfilling the sacramental aspect of Christ's saving grace and mission. (pp 166-169). The absolution along with the sign of the *pax* would mark the point of being again in God's favour.

Part Three: An Assessment²⁰

In general, it is easier to elaborate on the free act that a person makes with regard to the good. In such an act, the finality to which one tends brings about a greater self-realization and, in a theistic context, is seen as an option that one makes for God. In fine, when a person posits an act of virtue it is an act that is fulfilling. However, when one sins, it is more difficult to explain how self-realization is denied and how one says "no" to God. In great part, Teilhard de Chardin's (1881-1955) attempts at a grand synthesis have still to deal with a satisfactory explanation for the reality of sin (not necessarily Original Sin) in human history. Traditional scholasticism too referred to sin as an "absence" (*privatio*) not a reality (*ens*). Classical Catholic theology does not see grace as the counterpart of sin as though a neutral finite subject, a human person, could simply accept or reject God. At the same time Christian revelation and Catholic teaching have assured us of God's love and mercy in an existing human situation where persons can change (be converted by grace) and enter into communion with God's again.²¹²¹ J. Neuner and J. Dupuis:

The Christian Faith

in the Doctrinal Documents of the Catholic Church, Theological Publications in India, Bangalore, seventh and Enlarged Edition, 2004, Chapter V, Original Justice and Fall, p 195: "

While the doctrine of creation illustrates what life within this world should be according to God

's plan, the biblical account of the fall constitutes the interpretive key to evil, "the mystery of lawlessness...at work (2 Thess 2:7) in our world."

There are problems in Rahner's understanding of sin as 'the freedom to say "no" to God'. For instance, (1) human freedom seems to be irrevocably defined in the "yes" and the "no" when either is posited. How does one explain conversion to God after a "no" has been affirmed?

Rahner defines sin in the strict sense as the fully free and definitive "no" to the person of God, made by the total human being in a whole life act in an encounter with God as mediated by the world of things and other people. This negative decision is simultaneously about God and the whole human person, and irrevocably brings the human being to completion as a "no" to God.²²

It is not easy to see the "no" to God as irrevocable and therefore final unless possibly at the end of one's historical existence. Would this mean that Rahner does not envisage—in practice—the possibility of serious sin (mortal sin) being committed in the course of a person's historical existence?

(2) It would seem that Rahner's theological anthropology disregards the fact of conversion as spelt out in sacred scripture and the Church's tradition, even though Rahner accepts that a person can repent of his/her sins, can be forgiven, and can enter into communion with God again. The whole of salvation history is a series of events where a God permits sin and guilt to be present in the world of human persons and constantly offers his faithful and unconditional forgiving love. Rahner has no difficulty with the datum of sacred scripture and the official teaching of the Church. But in his efforts to make those doctrines relevant to our times, he attempts to interpret dogma and doctrine anew. It will be for students of Rahner to discover if the theological anthropology that he elaborates, allow for true forgiveness, a change of heart and a grace-filled existence of persons once again.

(3) Is Rahner putting a value on human freedom that is akin to the freedom of God in its absoluteness and irrevocability? At the end of his article, Ron Highfield says the following:

Finally, we have come to the tap root of the tensions in Rahner's doctrine of sin. Since the concrete human being is thought of as a union of God (supernatural existential) and (pure) human nature, Rahner considers himself able to attribute to this human, by a sort of "communication of properties," the freedom which is characteristic of the divine life alone. Under the flag of grace, an attribute of God can be safely transferred to the human being, so that human beings are said to have the freedom to decide definitively about God and the totality of their own being; thus they are free to realize themselves as a "yes" or "no" to God.

God is only what God wills to be. But no being other than God can be thought to decide about God freely and definitively. Only where freedom is absolute are the conditions fulfilled for the possibility of such a decision. And what are the implications if, nevertheless, Rahner understands the human being to be able to make this judgment?²³

(4) Rahner lived through the Nazi era and elaborated his transcendental method at a time when people were suffering from lack of freedom on many fronts. The Jews were targeted and made scapegoats, the Christian Churches were not forthright in their condemnation of Hitler's policies, and the trampling of political freedoms took place with impunity by a Germany conscious of its military might. These factors are strangely absent from Rahner's reflections on freedom, sin and guilt. Should these not have featured in Rahner's theology precisely because of the Heideggerian perspectives that he employed in understanding the human person in the sight of God?

Concluding Remarks

Rahner's anthropological theology is not aimed at explaining away the incomprehensibility of the divine. He is aware, along with Thomas Aquinas, that what we do not know about God is more than what we can know about God through our efforts. Rahner's theology is a reflection on the self in the light of revelation and he does not want to be hemmed in by the scholastic theology of the pre-Vatican II era. But Rahner is

very aware of the mysterious aspect of God and he is aware that no theology can provide a system of thought that can give an adequate and complete understanding of the creature (person) vis-à-vis the divine.

One must appreciate Rahner's attempt after having examined his views on mystery. Appreciating the mystery of God is a crucial fact in Rahner's theology. In the face of it, he even admits to a sense of helplessness:

In my theology I wish to proceed from the fact of an essential and absolute, ultimately insuperable sense of helplessness. When I approach God to the extent I understand him, I only reach him when I perceive him as the absolute mystery that surpasses me. And when I do not perceive him as the absolute mystery, then I have to say: Stop! You're on the wrong track, this path certainly does not lead to the true God of Christianity, the God of eternal life. If you intend to "explain" God with a certain rationalistic clarity, as is done sometimes even in Catholic theology, then you have certainly failed in your task. For me, God is precisely that mystery of the incomprehensible, the inexpressible, towards which at every moment of my life I am always tending.²⁴

Terms like *depositum fidei* can give the impression that Catholic faith is primarily a set of dogmatic truths (*fides quae*). There is also the danger in seeing Catholic Tradition as a consolidated body of truths about God as revealed in the Christ event. It is important to see the truth of God's revelation bringing us to affirm the mystery of his presence in our lives.

Would Rahner's understanding of God as incomprehensible or as mystery soft-peddle the meaning contained in the scriptures and magisterial teachings of the Church? Not really. But while God is absolute, articulations of the mystery are context-bound, i.e. present in the events of human and therefore personal history. Such articulations possess a meaning within the context of the faith community of the Church. But all religious language is symbolic. Hence it is not a question of discarding dogmas and doctrines but of perceiving their true function. That is what Rahner's theological anthropology seeks to do.

All the while, Rahner acknowledges that human freedom and the worst it is capable of (guilt in all its aspects) cannot annul the ever-present forgiving love of God. Further, while Rahner may not be able to

articulate comprehensively the ultimate status of the person who has accepted God's forgiveness after he/she has repented, he knows that the victory of the Risen Christ is the final point of arrival for the human person.

Notes and References

- 1 Martin Heidegger: *Being and Time*, (translated by John Macquarrie and Edward Robinson), Harper and Row, New York / London, 1962, p 26: "Everything we talk about, everything we have in view, everything towards which we comport ourselves in any way, is being; what we are is being, and so is how we are. Being lies in the fact that something is, and in its Being as it is; in Reality; in presence-at-hand; in subsistence; in validity; in Dasein; in the 'there is'."
- 2 Martin Heidegger: *Being and Time*, (translated by John Macquarrie and Edward Robinson), Harper and Row, New York / London, 1962, pp 26-27.
- 3 Karl Rahner: *Hearers of the Word*, (translated by Michael Richards), Herder and Herder, New York, 1969, pp 8-9.
- 4 Karl Rahner and Herbert Vorgrimler: *Theological Dictionary* edited by Cornelius Ernst, O.P. (translated by Richard Strachan), Herder and Herder, New York, 1965, "Theodicy", p 455.
- 5 Karl Rahner: *Foundations of Christian Faith, An Introduction to the Idea of Christianity*, (translated by William V. Dych), A Crossroad Book, New York, 1978, p 72: "Transcendence is the more original in relation to individual, categorical, univocal concepts. For transcendence, that is, this reaching out beyond towards the unlimited horizon of the whole movement of our spirit, is precisely the condition of possibility, the horizon, and the basis and ground by means of which we compare individual objects of experience with one another and classify them..." "...transcendental experience is the condition which makes possible all categorical knowledge of individual objects..."
- 6 Thomas F. O'Meara: *God in the World, A Guide to Karl Rahner's Theology*, Liturgical Press, Collegeville, 2007, p 59.
- 7 *Foundations of Christian Faith*, p 127.
- 8 (Translated by Michael Richards), Herder and Herder, New York, 1969, p 73, footnote 3.

- 9 I use the word “supposedly” on purpose, since a host of factors de facto affect the exercise of our intellect and will.
- 10 Karl Rahner: *Theological Investigations, Volume VI*, (translated by Karl-H and Boniface Kruger), “Theology as Freedom,” Darton, Longman & Todd, London and The Seabury Press, New York, 1974, p. 180.
- 11 *TI*, Volume VI, p 185.
- 12 *TI*, Volume VI, p 186.
- 13 Pope John Paul II’s encyclical *Veritatis Splendor* (1993) nos. 67-69 cautions against assuming that one’s transcendental orientation is separated from one’s concrete decisions made in the world. It does not seem to me that Rahner’s position falls under these strictures. Rahner is suggesting that in our present state we may not arrive at absolute clarity and certainty in our decisions. Full knowledge and total awareness are God’s alone!
- 14 *TI*, Volume VI, p 191.
- 15 Richard A. McCormick (Ref. Richard P. McBrien (general editor): *The HarperCollins Encyclopedia of Catholicism*, HarperCollins Publishers, New York, 1995, p 594) says the following:
- fundamental option**, a technical and even misleading term that refers to a dimension of freedom in human action deeper than mere freedom of object choice. This dimension is not the freedom of choice to do a particular thing or not, that is, a choice of specific objects. It is rather the free determination of oneself with regard to the totality of existence. It is a fundamental choice between love and selfishness, between self and God, who is our destiny...
- ...It is fundamental for several reasons. First, it is not an activity like the many daily activities that occupy people’s lives. It underlies all other choices. Second, since it underlies other, more superficial choices and manifests itself in them, there is a continual interplay between basic freedom and particular acts. Acting according to this option, one deepens it. Acting contrary to it, one undermines its stability. Finally, actions derive their moral seriousness from the presence or absence in them of this basic freedom. Thus, many theologians understand both mortal sin and conversion from it as necessarily being fundamental options.
- 16 *TI*, Volume VI, “Guilt – Responsibility – Punishment within the view of Catholic Theology,” p 199.
- 17 *TI*, Volume VI, *ibid.*, p 201.
- 18 *TI*, Volume VI, *ibid.*, p 205.
- 19 This section will present the points treated by Karl Rahner in his article “Forgotten Truths concerning the Sacrament of Penance.” (*TI*, Volume II,

Man in the Church, (translated by Karl-H. Kruger), Helican Press, Baltimore, 1966.)

- 20 In this part, much of my assessment has been stimulated by an article of Ron Highfield: THE FREEDOM TO SAY “NO”? KARL RAHNER’S DOCTRINE OF SIN, in *Theological Studies* 56 (1995), 485-505.
- 21 J. Neuner and J. Dupuis: The Christian Faith, in the Doctrinal Documents of the Catholic Church, Theological Publications in India, Bangalore, seventh and Enlarged Edition, 2004, Chapter V, Original Justice and Fall, p 195: “*While the doctrine of creation illustrates what life within this world should be according to God’s plan, the biblical account of the fall constitutes the interpretive key to evil, “the mystery of lawlessness...at work (2 Thess 2:7) in our world.”*”
- 22 Ron Highfield, p 489.
- 23 Ron Highfield, pp 504-505.
- 24 Rahner in *Dialogue*, pp 216-7.